

TERRIFIC
BIOBASED FLAGSHIP PACKAGING SOLUTIONS

Next generation circular biobased flagship packaging: a catalyst for the green transition

Grant Agreement n 101157635

HORIZON-JU-CBE-2023

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List of Acronyms

CBE JU	Circular Biobased Europe Joint Undertaking
BIC	Biobased Industries Consortium

Disclaimer

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**Next generation circular bio-based flagship packaging:
a catalyst for the green transition**

TERRIFIC, THE EUROPEAN PROJECT ON BIO-BASED PACKAGING SOLUTIONS, TO BE PRESENTED AT ECOMONDO 2024

NOVARA, 05/11/2024

Just six months after its official launch, TERRIFIC, the European project (HORIZON-JU-CBE-2023) that aims to demonstrate the effectiveness of bio-based packaging solutions, comes to Ecomondo, the leading circular economy event, which will be held in Rimini from 5–8 November 2024.

TERRIFIC, coordinated by Novamont (Versalis Eni), will have a stand managed by its partner Legacoop (stand D3_103) and will feature in two events at the fair on 7 November: “The integrated sustainability of the cooperative food sector. Challenges and opportunities in waste management: from packaging to RENTRI”, organised by Legacoop, and “Next Generation Circular Bio-Based Packaging: The TERRIFIC Project’s role in advancing the European circular bioeconomy”, organised directly by Novamont (10.00 – 13:00, Acero Room, Pav. A6, 1st floor).

The first talk will analyse the impact on cooperatives of the European packaging regulation and RENTRI (National Electronic Register for Waste Traceability), and will also present good practices from the cooperative sector. The second event will focus on the challenges and opportunities associated with the TERRIFIC project, highlighting its impact on the European bioeconomy. The event will feature experts from the sustainable and bio-based packaging sector, including representatives from the Portuguese retail sector, who will discuss the Portuguese approach to circularity in packaging. In addition, Biorepack will present the first European

extended producer responsibility (EPR) system devoted to biodegradable and compostable plastic packaging.

TERRIFIC is one of the four flagship projects financed in 2024 by Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU), the public-private partnership between the European Union and the Bio-based Industries Consortium (BIC), which supports the development of Europe's bio-based sector. This initiative has secured over €16 million in financing and aims to develop and demonstrate eight innovative solutions using renewable raw materials for the packaging sector. One of the objectives of the project is to use sub-products from agro-industrial value chains to produce compostable and recyclable biopolyesters and biomaterials with over 95% renewable content.

TERRIFIC involves 19 partners, including four SMEs, from 9 European countries.

"The TERRIFIC project represents a significant step forward in advancing Europe's circular bioeconomy. The innovative combination of renewable byproducts and circular industrial biorefinery concept will lead to the production of high-performance bio-based packaging solutions for everyday use. This project not only showcases the potential of bioplastics in driving decarbonisation and pollution prevention, but also aligns with the EU's circularity and recycling targets, setting a new standard for the bio-based packaging industry." Nicoló Giacomuzzi-Moore, CBE JU Executive Director
